

**RASHTRIYA AYURVEDA VIDYAPEETH AND ITS CONTRIBUTIONS
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Attribution 4.0 International license.**ABSTRACT**

Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth (RAV) is an autonomous institution under the Ministry of AYUSH, Government of India, established with the objective of reviving and propagating classical Ayurvedic knowledge through the traditional *Guru-Shishya Parampara*. In contrast to the institutional, syllabus-based education system, RAV emphasizes holistic learning by imparting comprehensive textual, practical, and clinical training rooted in ancient Gurukula traditions. The Vidyapeeth conducts structured academic and clinical programs, notably the Acharya Guru-Shishya Parampara leading to the Member of Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth (MRAV) and the Chikitsak Guru-Shishya Parampara awarding the Certificate of Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth (CRAV). These programs aim to develop competent teachers, researchers, and skilled clinicians through one-to-one mentorship under eminent Ayurvedic scholars and

practitioners. RAV operates within the contemporary regulatory framework of Ayurvedic education, complementing the National Commission for Indian System of Medicine (NCISM), and awards certification upon successful completion of its courses. Training is imparted across diverse clinical specialties such as Kayachikitsa, Ksharsutra, Shalakyas, Stree Roga, Asthi and Marma Chikitsa, among others, depending on the availability of expert Gurus. The Vidyapeeth follows a rigorous process for the empanelment of Gurus and

selection of Shishya, ensuring high standards of education, ethics, and clinical exposure. Financial support in the form of honorarium and stipend is provided to Gurus and Shishya respectively.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Gurus, Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth, NCISM.

INTRODUCTION

Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth is an autonomous organization fully funded by the Ministry of AYUSH, Govt. of India, with the objective of reviving classical practical and textual knowledge of Ayurveda through ancient Gurukula method of learning. The Vidyapeeth appoints renowned scholars and experts/practitioners in the field of Ayurveda as Gurus and runs courses under traditional method of 'Guru Shishya Parampara'. Ayurveda is a centuries old traditional medicine system of India which is well regulated under the aegis of the Ministry of Ayush (MoA), with more than 400 000 registered practitioners. After enactment of the NCISM Act, 2020 and the formation of the NCISM, NCISM became the authority for granting permission to start a new college or increase seats in existing courses and new courses as well as for renewal of annual permission for existing courses. NCISM has four autonomous boards:8 (i) The Board of Ayurveda; (ii) The Board of Unani, Siddha and Sowa-Rigpa; (iii) The Medical Assessment and Rating Board for Indian System of Medicine; and (iv) The Board of Ethics and Registration for Indian System of Medicine. These Boards look after the work related to UG and PG education, Medical Assessment, Rating and Ethics and Registration of practitioners. Additionally, RAV plays a pivotal role in quality assurance through the Ayurveda Training Accreditation Board (ATAB), which accredits Ayurveda training programs not covered under the NCISM Act, both in India and abroad. Through its academic initiatives, accreditation activities, and extensive publications, RAV contributes significantly to the preservation, standardization, and global promotion of Ayurveda, reinforcing its relevance in contemporary healthcare and education systems.

At the end of successful completion of the course, the students will be awarded the certificate (CRAV).

The clinical specialties in which the training would be provided include.

1. Kayachikitsa
2. Stree Roga and Prasuti Tantra
3. Ksharsutra

4. Marma Chikitsa
5. Bhagna and Asthi Chikitsa
6. Shalaky (Netra Roga)
7. Shalaky (Danta Roga) and such other clinical specialties depending upon availability of the gurus.

OBJECTIVES

1. To promote the knowledge of Ayurveda.
2. To formulate schemes for continuing education and conducting examinations for the purpose in various disciplines of Ayurveda.
3. To recognize and encourage merit in various branches of Ayurveda.
4. To undertake academic work in Ayurveda of National & International importance.
5. To organize workshops and seminars in various branches of Ayurveda.
6. To maintain communication with professional associations, Societies, Colleges and Universities for raising standards of Ayurvedic Education.
7. To secure and manage funds and endowments for the promotion of Ayurveda and implementation of continuing education in Ayurveda.
8. To conduct experiments of new methods of Ayurvedic education in order to arrive at satisfactory standards of education.
9. To institute professorships, other faculty position fellowships, research cadre positions and scholarships etc. for realizing the objectives of the Vidyapeeth.

Mission of the RAV

- To promote transfer of Ancient Traditional Ayurveda knowledge through Guru Shishya Parampara.
- To operate accreditation of Ayurveda Courses, which do not fall under the purview of NCISM Act 2020 (Earlier IMCC Act 1970) focusing on Standardization of Courses to bring Quality culture to Ayurveda Education system.
- To operate the programme of certification of Ayurveda professionals working nationally and internationally focusing on quality of Ayurveda education.
- To established RAV as a formally recognized Institute for carrying out the training and research in traditional and emerging Ayurvedic clinical practice.

Guru Shishya Parampara

- Guru Shishya Parampara is the traditional residential method of education wherein the Shishya lives in the vicinity of his Guru and undertakes the studies in one to one manner by accompanying the guru in his regular routine clinical work. This system vanished with the disappearance of Gurukula.
- RAV realized that in Ayurveda, this method of knowledge transfer had been very effective and hence the Vidyapeeth is making efforts to revive this system through its courses.
- In institutional form of learning only relevant portions of the Samhitas (classical texts of Ayurveda) are being taught in the form of syllabus. On the contrary, the Guru Shishya Parampara programme of RAV provides the students to study whole text to get adequate knowledge of selected Samhita and its Teeka (commentary) and exposes them traditional skills of the Ayurvedic practices.
- The Shishya get sufficient time for interaction with the guru and get a live demonstration upon the patients, herbs or formulations during the course of the study.

Gurukula

(A) Acharya Guru Shishya Parampara (Two-year course of Member of Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth-MRAV)

- This is an academic programme based upon literary research imparting the knowledge of Ayurvedic Samhitas and commentaries to participants.
- The main aim of this course is to prepare good teachers, research scholars and experts in Ayurveda Samhitas. The Shishya studies the Samhita, related to his/her specialization in course under the guidance of the Guru for a period of 2 years.
- Candidates possessing adequate theoretical and practical knowledge and good understanding of Sanskrit are admitted to this course.
- At the end of the course, they are required to submit a dissertation which is regarded as a contribution of the Shishya.
- Though, the Shishya studies the entire Samhita (text) under the expert guidance of Guru, he/she writes dissertation only on prescribed chapters/topics as suggested by Vidyapeeth in consultation with respective Guru in order to avoid duplication of the same work.

(B) Chikitsak Guru Shishya Parampara (One-year course of Certificate of Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth-CRAV)

- This course was started in February, 1999. This course has the duration of one year for both Ayurvedic graduates and postgraduates.
- In this course, the candidates possessing Ayurvedacharya (BAMS) or equivalent degree/PG in Ayurveda are selected for training under eminent practicing Vaidyas, who are empanelled as Chikitsak/Institutional Gurus.
- During the course of study, the students learn the procedures like Nadi Pariksha, Aushadhi Nirman, Ksharsutra, Panchakarma, treatment of diseases, Netra Chikitsa, Asthi Chikitsa pertaining to the Ayurvedic system.
- Every month, the trainees are required to prepare record of the patients they studied for its subsequent submission to RAV.
- The work done by the Shishya like patient history sheets, monthly study reports etc. is examined in Vidyapeeth.
- Suggestions for improvement are communicated to the Shishya through their respective Gurus.

Gurus**(A) Guru for Member of Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth (MRAV) course**

- A person is eligible to be appointed as Guru for MRAV course,
 - who is a retired Professor of Ayurveda possessing PG or PhD qualification with good published recognized research work and excellent academic experience.
 - Or a retired Director of Research Institution of Ayurveda
 - Or any other person of eminence in Ayurveda having held the post of departmental head of the State, Central/Autonomous organization.
 - and other office of repute with vast knowledge and adequate experience in academic or any specialty of Ayurveda.
 - Or eminent scholar of Ayurveda.
 - The Guru should be above 60 years of age, proficient in Sanskrit and in classical texts of Ayurveda.
 - Further, he/she must have very special knowledge and skills to justify selection.
 - In the subject of Dravyaguna, Rasa-Shastra, Bhaishjya Kalpana and other clinical subjects, the Gurus should have basic facility for demonstration or should have access to such facility/Institution in the near vicinity.

Guru for Certificate of Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth (CRAV) course: Eligibility criteria for Gurus (CRAV)

Following two eligibility criteria have been adopted for selection of CRAV Gurus

- 1) For Institutional Gurus.
- 2) Criteria for Individual Gurus.

1. Criteria for Individual Gurus

- Ayurveda practitioners enrolled in any State Register of Indian Medicine under Section 17 of IMCC Act, 1970.
- Age not below 50 years.
- Having a minimum standing of 20 years of Ayurvedic general or specialized clinical practice in any clinical branch of Ayurveda.
- Shall not be employed at any place and in any position on a regular basis.
- Ayurveda practitioners aspirant to be an RAV Guru should have a minimum OPD of 40 patients per day.

In case of surgical practice besides OPD of 25 patients per day, the Vaidya must be performing at least 15 surgical/ Para-surgical/Ksharsutra/Agni Karma procedures daily.

- In case of Ayurvedic Pharmacy, the Vaidya should have his own pharmacy with a minimum standing of 20 years.
- Willingness to train the young Ayurvedic doctors through a hands-on training method and to share their clinical knowledge and skills without any reservation.
- Gurus with or without IPD can be given up to 02 students and with occupancy of IPD of 20 beds and above can be given up to 04 students.

2. Criteria for Institutional Gurus (Institutional Training Centres)

- Declared as Centre of Excellence by Ministry of Ayush.
- Ayurvedic hospital with at least 50 IPD beds and 200 OPD patients per day.
- The centre should have a minimum 10 years of standing.
- The centre should be of good repute and should be well known for its Ayurvedic management of various specialized conditions.
- In case of a pharmacy, it should have a GMP certification, facility for drug quality monitoring.
- The institution authorities should be ready to give every access to CRAV students to all the places which are related to their clinical/pharmacy training.

- Up to 08 students may be given to such institutions and the chief physician/doctor of the institution and/or other senior doctors will be in-charge of training of Shishya.

Empanelment

- The selection of Guru of any course is done by a Committee comprising of experts nominated by the Governing Body or its President.
- The Committee scrutinizes bio-data of scholars and Vaidyas and selects the Guru after proper discussion on his/her competence and recommends to Governing Body for empanelment.
- After the approval of the Governing Body the letter of empanelment is sent to guru whenever vacancy arises after receiving his/her willingness for teacher-ship and adherence to rules of the Vidyapeeth and ascertaining that facilities for training are available with him/her.
- Selection of Guru is purely on temporary basis for the period of one term i.e. one year in CRAV course and two years in MRAV course.
- The appointment stands completed when there is no student under the Guru or when all the students under him/her have completed their studies/duration of study.

Shishyas

- The advertisement for admission to CRAV course was given in newspapers on all India basis, inviting applications from eligible candidates.
- As per the rules of RAV, candidates with Ayurvedacharya (BAMS) or an equivalent degree are selected in CRAV course. The maximum age limit for admission in this course is 30 years for U.G. degree holders and 32 years for P.G. degree holders.
- Relaxation up to 35 years is given to permanently employed doctors duly sponsored by Government. The qualifications of candidates must have been recognized by CCIM.
- After the scrutiny of the applications received, the eligible candidates are called for a written test. Various aspects of syllabus of graduate course with special emphasis on clinical subjects are covered in the written test based on objective questions.
- In the selection of the Shishya, the merit of the student, distance of 250 km (between Gurus and Students) and the preference of subject/Guru are taken into the consideration. Preference is given to Medical Officers in CRAV course.
- The selected candidates are required to submit a Bond to the effect that in the event of the student leaving the course in the middle or if the student is expelled for violation of rules

of the Vidyapeeth, the whole amount of stipend received from the Vidyapeeth shall be refunded with 12% interest thereon.

- On having completed the formalities, the Shishyas are placed under the tutelage of concerned Gurus located in different parts of the country for training.
- The duration of the course is one year during which the students have to attend the clinical and other duties in the concerned specialty as per the directions of the guru.
- The students have to submit Monthly and Quarterly Report of the work done to the Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth.
- They also have to write one dissertation on the subject given by Guru/RAV.

Reservation

- Reservation of seats to SC, ST, OBC, Economically Weaker Sections (EWS) and Physically Handicapped (PH) candidates will be implemented for total number of vacancies available as per government policy prevalent from time to time.
- Reservation for government sponsored candidates (permanent medical officers) is available.
- Sponsored candidates will not be paid any stipend.

Honorarium and Stipend

There is a provision of payment of honorarium to Gurus and stipend to Shishyas during the training period every month. Each guru is given 2-4 students for training.

- The honorarium to Guru is ` 15,820/- only plus DA 6th CPC at the rates applicable from time to time plus ` 5,000/- upto two students.
- If any Guru has more than two students, he/she shall be paid an extra honorarium at ` 2,000/- only per student.
- Similarly, the stipend for CRAV students is ` 15,820/- only plus DA 6th CPC at the rates applicable from time to time.

For MRAV students the stipend is ` 15,820/- only plus DA 6th CPC at the applicable rates plus ` 2,500/- only.

Ayurveda Training Accreditation Board (ATAB)

- Ayurveda Training Accreditation Board (ATAB), operating under Rashtriya Ayurveda Vidyapeeth (RAV), is a board established by the Ministry of Ayush, Govt. of India.

- Its primary objective is to accredit Ayurveda training courses being conducted both within India and abroad, which does not fall under the purview of National Commission for Indian System of Medicine (NCISM) Act 2020.
- ATAB serves as a mechanism to ensure the uniformity, quality and standardization of Ayurveda training programs, thereby enhancing the credibility and effectiveness of Ayurvedic education.
- Overall, the establishment of ATAB represents a significant step towards ensuring the quality and integrity of Ayurveda training programs, both within India and internationally, contributing to the promotion and preservation of Ayurvedic knowledge and practices.

RAV Guru List

1	Dr. B. Prabhakaran, Kannur (Kerala)	Agada Tantra
2	Dr. N. Krishnaiah, Tirupati (Andhra Pradesh)	Bal Roga
3	Dr. Jaysukh R. Makwana, Rajkot (Gujarat)	Danta Chikitsa
4	Dr. L. Sucharitha, Bengaluru (Karnataka)	Stree Roga
5	Dr. N.V. Sreevaths, Palakkad (Kerala)	Asthi & Marma Chikitsa
6	Dr. Vijayan Nangelil, Kothamanagalam (Kerala)	Asthi & Marma Chikitsa
7	Dr. Mathews Joseph, Muvattupuzha (Kerala)	Asthi & Marma Chikitsa and Sports Injury Management
8	Dr. C. Suresh Kumar, Trivandrum (Kerala)	Asthi Chikitsa
9	Dr. A. Raghavendra Acharya, Udupi (Karnataka)	Ksharsutra and Marma Chikitsa
10	Vd. Devendra Kumar Shah, Ahmedabad (Gujarat)	Ksharsutra
11	Dr. K.V.S. Rao, Bhilai (C.G.)	Ksharsutra
12	Dr. Manoranjan Sahu, Varanasi (U.P.)	Ksharsutra
13	Dr. Harshvardhan Jobanputra, Nadiad (Gujarat)	Ksharsutra
14	Dr. M. Bhaskar Rao, Tirupati (Andhra Pradesh)	Ksharsutra
15	Dr. Raman Singh, Varanasi (U.P.)	Ksharsutra
16	Dr. Hem Raj Sharma, Una (H.P.)	Ksharsutra
17	Dr. Lalta Prasad, Bareilly (U.P.)	Ksharsutra
18	Dr. S. Dattatray Rao, Tirupati (Andhra Pradesh)	Ksharsutra
19	Dr. Sat Pal Gupta, Ambala (Haryana)	Ksharsutra
20	Dr. Nagender Pal, Mandi (Himachal Pradesh)	Ksharsutra
21	Vd. Alok Mohanlal Gupta, Yavatmal (M.S.)	Ksharsutra
22	Dr. Kosaraju Venkata Chalapathi Rao, Vijayawada (Andhra Pradesh)	Ksharsutra
23	Dr. Vijay Vishwanath Doiphode, Pune (M.S.)	Pharmacy
24	Vd. Vivek Dattatraya Sane, Pune (M.S.)	Pharmacy
25	Vd. Surya Prakash Sharma, Kolkata (West Bengal)	Pharmacy
26	Vd. Sasikumar Nechiyal, Palakkad (Kerala)	Pharmacy
27	Dr. D. Ramanathan, Thrissur (Kerala)	Pharmacy
28	Dr. I. Bhavadasan Namboothiri, Kannur (Kerala)	Netra Chikitsa
29	Dr. Hemkant Shivajirao Baviskar, Jalgaon (M.S.)	Netra Chikitsa

30	Sreedhareeyam Ayurvedic Eye Hospital & Research Centre, Ernakulam (Kerala) (Dr. N. Narayanan Namboothiri)	Netra Chikitsa (Institutional Guru)
31	Arya Vaidya Chikitsalayam and Research Institute, Coimbatore (Tamilnadu) (Dr. Ramkumar)	Kayachikitsa (Institutional Guru)
32	Arya Vaidya Sala, Kottakkal, Kerala (Dr. P.M. Varier and Dr. Rajagopalan K.V.)	Kayachikitsa (Institutional Guru)
33	Smt. Maniben Amrutlal Hargovan Government Ayurveda Hospital, Ahmedabad (Gujarat) (Dr. Varsha Dave)	Kayachikitsa (Institutional Guru)
34	Vd. Anant Sadanand Nimkar, Satara (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
35	Dr. Mani Bhushan Kumar, Patna (Bihar)	Kayachikitsa
36	Vd. Binod Joshi, Haldwani (Uttarakhand)	Kayachikitsa
37	Vd. Namadhar Sharma, New Delhi	Kayachikitsa
38	Dr. Ramesh R. Varier, Madurai (Tamilnadu)	Kayachikitsa
39	Dr. V. Sreekumar, Thrissur (Kerala)	Kayachikitsa
40	Dr. Ravishankar Pervaje, Dakshinakannada (Karnataka)	Kayachikitsa
41	Dr. Ramdas M. Avhad, Ahmednagar (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
42	Vd. Ashwani Kumar Sharma, Karol Bagh (New Delhi)	Kayachikitsa
43	Vd. Tarachand Sharma, Rohini (New Delhi)	Kayachikitsa
44	Vd. Narendra Narayandas Gujarathi, Jalgaon (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
45	Dr. Ganjam Krishna Prasad, Secunderabad (Telangana)	Kayachikitsa
46	Dr. Madhusudan Deshpande, Bhopal (M.P.)	Kayachikitsa
47	Dr. C.M. Sreekrishnan, Thrissur (Kerala)	Kayachikitsa
48	Dr. Jagadeeshwari Prasad Mishra "Basant", Sitamarhi (Bihar)	Kayachikitsa
49	Dr. Santosh Bhagwanrao Nevpurkar, Aurangabad (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
50	Dr. Vinay Vasudeo Welankar, Thane (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
51	Dr. Panchabhai V. Damaniya, Junagadh (Gujarat)	Kayachikitsa
52	Vd. Anil Bhardwaj, Chandigarh	Kayachikitsa
53	Vd. Achyut Kumar Tripathi, Noida (U.P.)	Kayachikitsa
54	Dr. Manoj Kumar Sharma, Kota (Rajasthan)	Kayachikitsa
55	Dr. Pangala Muralidhara Ramachandra Bhat, Bengaluru (Karnataka)	Kayachikitsa
56	Dr. Pravin Prabhakar Joshi, Dhule (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
57	Dr. Ravindra Vatsyayan, Ludhiana (Punjab)	Kayachikitsa
58	Vd. Mahesh Madhusudan Thakur, Thane (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
59	Vd. Upendra Digambar Dixit, Ponda (Goa)	Kayachikitsa
60	Dr. P.M.S. Raveendranath, Palakkad (Kerala)	Kayachikitsa
61	Vd. Mualidhar Purushottam Prabhudesai, Sindhururg (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
62	Vd. M. Prasad, Thrissur (Kerala)	Kayachikitsa
63	Vd. Suvinay Vinayak Damale, Sindhururg (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
64	Vd. Satya Prakash Gupta, Moradabad (U.P.)	Kayachikitsa
65	Dr. Dhanraj Vishweshwar Gahukar, Nagpur (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
66	Vd. Malhar Prabhakar Joshi, Sangli (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
67	Dr. A.B. Sasidharan Nair, Kottayam (Kerala)	Kayachikitsa
68	Vd. Anupama Jayant Deopujari, Nagpur (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
69	Vd. (Prof.) G.G. Gangadharan, Bengaluru (Karnataka)	Kayachikitsa
70	Dr. Ramavatar Sharma, Sikar (Rajasthan)	Kayachikitsa
71	Vd. (Prof.) Shyam Sunder Sharma, Bhagalpur (Bihar)	Kayachikitsa
72	Dr. Savithri Sambamurthy Gayitri, Bengaluru (Karnataka)	Kayachikitsa

73	Vd. Shrikrishna Sharma Khandel, Jaipur (Rajasthan)	Kayachikitsa
74	Dr. T. Shridhara Bairy, Udupi (Karnataka)	Kayachikitsa
75	Prof. (Dr.) Narayan Chandra Dash, Puri (Odisha)	Kayachikitsa
76	Dr. M.B. Gururaja, Shivamoga (Karnataka)	Kayachikitsa
77	Dr. Vinay Vora, Ahmedabad (Gujarat)	Kayachikitsa
78	Dr. Preeti Chhabra, New Delhi	Kayachikitsa
79	Dr. A.R. Ramadas, Coimbatore (Tamilnadu)	Kayachikitsa
80	Vd. Satish Shamlal Bhattad, Ahmednagar (M.S.)	Kayachikitsa
81	Dr. Pranav Kiritkumar Dave, Ahmedabad (Gujarat)	Kayachikitsa
82	Vd. S.N. Pande, Ujjain (Madhya Pradesh)	Kayachikitsa
83	Vd. Ravinder Bajaj, Ludhiana (Punjab)	Kayachikitsa

Publications of RAV

- Pranavaha srotas Disorders And their Management
- Plants and other Drugs of Sushruta samhita Saphthadhyayi
- National Seminar on Management of Cancer Through Ayurveda.
- Interactive Workshop on Ayurveda (Asthivaha Srotas, of bones and joints including Fractures and their management).
- National Seminar on Basti Karma
- Interactive Workshop on Ayurvedic Formulations – Classical Prescriptions & Current Practices.
- Interactive Workshop on Prognosis through Arishta Lakshanas and their Scientific Basis.
- Plants of Bhavaprakash.
- Interactive Workshop on Evidence Based Clinical Practice in Ayurveda.
- National Seminar on Evidence Based Ayurvedic Approach to Diagnosis, Preventions and Management of Diabetes and its complications.
- Interactive Workshop On Ayurveda (Clinical diagnosis in Ayurveda Subjective & Objective Approach).
- Ayurvedic concepts of Healthy Mother and Happy Child.
- Interactive Workshop on Ayurveda (Hepatological Disorders).
- Interactive Workshop on Kumarbhritya.
- Interactive Workshop between students and teachers (Under Graduate).
- Interactive Workshop between students and teachers (Post Graduate).
- Interactive Workshop on Kriya Shareer in Ayurveda.
- Kshara Sutra therapy in fistula-in-ano and other ano-rectal disorders Dr. S.K.Sharma, Prof.K.R.Sharma and Prof. Kulwant Singh.

- Interactive Workshop on Mamsavaha srotas and neuro-muscular system, diseases and their management through Ayurveda.
- Interactive Workshop on Marma and management of Marmabhighat in Ayurveda.
- Medicinal plants used in Ayurveda.
- Ayurvedic Scientific Seminar on Mental Health.
- Interactive Workshop on Nadi Pariksha in Ayurveda – Reality and Relevance.
- Interactive Workshop on Avritatva and Gatatva of Vata.
- Plants of Sharangdhara.
- Interactive Workshop on Ayurveda (Raktava Srotas, related to Cardio-vascular system, Disorders and their management).
- Ayurvedic Scientific Seminar on Rasayana.
- Ayurvedic Scientific seminar on Reproductive Health of Woman through Ayurveda.
- Workshop on Prasuti Tantra, Stree Roga, & Kaumara Bhritya.
- Sushrutasamhita Sutrasthan Text and Dalhana's commentary along with there Hindi translation, Interactive Workshop on Shukravaha Srotas and Artavavaha Srotas, their srotodusthi Vikara Management.
- Interactive Workshop on Ayurveda (Urinary System Disorders).

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